

IMPETUS impact assessment matrix

The figure in the next page (Fig.1) is the IMPETUS impact assessment matrix. It guides the CSIs teams in planning their impact assessment activities by indicating:

- Who will provide the data for the assessment?
- When the data gathering should (ideally) take place?

The answer to the first question is visualised with two icons, one representing the CSI team and one the volunteers. The second question is answered via the green and red icons in the right column. A green sign in the Ex-ante column means that the data should be gathered at the beginning of the engagement of the volunteers or before they start an activity the project wants to evaluate in terms of impact (for example a training workshop). A green sign in the ex-post column means that the CSI should gather the data at the end of their activities.

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Fig. 1 – IMPETUS impact assessment matrix

